

Synthesis of Some New Isocoumarins

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6-Methyl-7-hydroxyisocoumarin, 6-methyl-7-methoxyisocoumarins and 5-methoxy-8-methylisocoumarin have been synthesised in three simple stages. 3-Hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid, 3-methoxy-4-methylbenzoic acid and 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid have been condensed with chloral hydrate in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid to give the corresponding trichloromethylphthalides. The trichloromethylphthalides on reduction with zinc dust and acetic acid furnished 2-(β -dichloromethyl)-benzoic acid which on refluxing in ethanol with concentrated hydrochloric acid yielded the corresponding isocoumarins. The solution of these isocoumarins in ethanol on refluxing with liquor ammonia gave 1-(2H)-isoquinolones.

A new synthesis to isocoumarins without any substituent in the lactone ring has been reported from this laboratory¹. The route involves the hydrolysis of 2-(β -dichloroethyl)-benzoic acids in ethanol with concentrated hydrochloric acid to furnish isocoumarins. 2-(β -Dichloroethyl)-benzoic acids are obtained from trichloromethylphthalides, prepared by condensing appropriately substituted benzoic acids with chloral hydrate in the presence of sulphuric acid (90%).

The present communication is an application of the above route leading to the synthesis of three new isocoumarins: 6-methyl-7-hydroxyisocoumarin(IVa); 6-methyl-7-methoxyisocoumarin(IVb) and 5-methoxy-8-methylisocoumarin(IVc).

Appropriately substituted benzoic acids (Ia, Ib and Ic) were condensed with chloral hydrate in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid to give the respective trichloromethylphthalides (IIa, IIb and IIc) which on reduction with zinc dust and glacial acetic acid furnished 2-(β -dichloroethyl)-benzoic acids (IIIa, IIIb and IIIc). These dichloro compounds on refluxing in ethanol with concentrated hydrochloric acid for varying periods furnished the isocoumarins (IVa, IVb and IVc). (IVa, b, c) on

refluxing with liquor ammonia yielded 1-(2H)-isoquinolones (Va, Vb and Vc). The I.R. and U.V. Spectral data were compatible with the structure of isocoumarins.

3-Methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid(Ic) gives poor yield of isocoumarin, i.e., only 50 per cent under the best experimental condition. The low yield may be ascribed to the steric effect of the methoxy group in position 3 of the 2-(β -dichloroethyl)-3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid(IIIc) which hinders the hydrolysis of the $-\text{CHCl}_2$ group.

Experimental

6-Methyl-7-hydroxyisocoumarin(IVa): A solution of 2-(β -dichloroethyl)-5-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid² (2.0 g) in ethanol (40 ml; 95%) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 ml) for 10 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and left overnight. The white crystalline mass separating was filtered, washed well with water and dried. It was triturated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and filtered immediately, washed and dried. The crude product was recrystallised from ethylacetate as white needles; m.p. 124°, (yield 1.1 g; 90.0%).

$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 320, 295 nm; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3410, 1720, 1615 cm^{-1}

(Found: C, 68.12; H, 4.49% Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$: C, 68.18; H, 4.54%)

6-Methyl-7-methoxyisocoumarin(IVb): A solution of 6-methyl-7-hydroxyisocoumarin (0.50 g) in dry acetone (20 ml) was refluxed with methyl iodide (0.80 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.45 g, ignited) on a water bath for 16 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered and washed with acetone. The filtrate and washing was collected and evaporated. The crude product was crystallized from ethanol, (0.35 g); m.p. 92-93°.

$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 312, 278 nm; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1720, 1615, 1560 cm^{-1}

- (a) $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{OH}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{CH}_3$.
 (b) $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_3 = \text{OCH}_3$, $\text{R}_4 = \text{CH}_3$.
 (c) $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$; $\text{R}_4 = \text{OCH}_3$.

6-Methyl-7-hydroxyisocarbostyryl(Va): 6-Methyl-7-hydroxyisocoumarin (0.3 g) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed with liquor ammonia (20 ml) for 2.5 hours on a water bath. The reaction mixture was left overnight and the solid that separated was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol, (0.2 g); m.p. 143-44°. (Found: C, 68.60; H, 5.11; N, 7.88% Calcd. for $C_{10}H_9NO_2$: C, 68.57; H, 5.14; N, 8.00%).

6-Methyl-7-methoxyisocoumarin(IVb): 2-($\beta\beta$ -Dichloroethyl)-4-methyl-5-methoxybenzoic acid^a (2.5 g) was dissolved in ethanol (40 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid for 12 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and left overnight. White crystalline mass that separated was filtered, washed well with water and dried. It was then triturated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and filtered immediately, washed with water and dried. The crude product was recrystallized from ethylacetate-petroleum ether as white needles, (1.50 g; 82.5%); m.p. 92-93°.

Mixed m.p. of the above compound with the authentic specimen prepared earlier remained un-depressed.

λ_{\max}^{MeOH} 316, 274 nm; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1720, 1615, 1560 cm^{-1}

(Found: C, 69.38; H, 5.17% Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_2$: C, 69.47; H, 5.26%)

6-Methyl-7-methoxyisocarbostyryl(Vb): A solution of 6-methyl-7-methoxyisocoumarin (0.25 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed with liquor ammonia (15 ml) for 2 hours and left overnight. The solid that separated was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol as fine needles, (0.12 g); m.p. 124-25°.

(Found: C, 69.88; H, 5.77; N, 7.31% Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{11}NO_2$: C, 69.84; H, 5.82; N, 7.40%).

5-Methoxy-8-methylisocoumarin(IVc): A solution of 2-($\beta\beta$ -dichloroethyl)-3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid^a (2.0 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml) for 12 hours on a water bath. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and ethanol was evaporated. It was cooled, filtered, washed with water and triturated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate. The unchanged white mass was filtered, washed and crystallized from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as colourless needles, (0.85 g; 50%); m.p. 106-7°.

λ_{\max}^{MeOH} 322, 278 nm; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1710, 1620, 1575 cm^{-1}

(Found: C, 69.42; H, 5.19% Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_2$: C, 69.47; H, 5.26%)

5-Methoxy-8-methylisocarbostyryl(Vc): A solution of 5-methoxy-8-methylisocoumarin (0.2 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed with liquor ammonia (10 ml) for 2 hours, and left overnight. The solid separated was filtered and crystallized from ethanol (0.15 g); m.p. 139-40°.

(Found: C, 69.86; H, 5.75; N, 7.29% Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{11}NO_2$: C, 69.84; H, 5.82, N, 7.40%).

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References

1. B. K. SARKHEL and J. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15B**, 103.
2. H. K. DESAI and R. N. USGAONKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 439.